

Copyright Protection of AI-Generated Works: A Comparative Study Between India and Canada

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Abstract

With the rapid technological advancements, Generative AI can generate images, texts, sounds, or any other creations that are unique in its own way. The provisions of Indian Copyright Law require presence of human author before granting copyright protection to any kind of work. This has led to a lot of confusion as to who would be considered as the author of the AI-generated work? The Developer, the person who gave the input, or the AI itself? This paper aims to study the approaches followed by two different jurisdictions i.e., India and Canada, while granting copyright protection to AI-generated work. India strictly follows human centric approach while Canada recognise the AI made creations which are made with significant human input.

1. Introduction

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) has completely changed how artistic works are developed, and circulated. Complex generative large language models (LLMs), diffusion-based image generators like Midjourney and DALL-E, AI-assisted music and video generators, and many other autonomous creative systems have made it harder to tell the difference between creative work made by humans and work made by machines.¹ As AI systems learn from massive datasets and autonomously generate text, images, art, music, and even inventions, the global legal community is confronted with a foundational challenge: whether works created wholly or substantially by AI can or should receive copyright

¹ Sam Ricketson and Jane C. Ginsburg, *International Copyright and Neighbouring Rights: The Berne Convention and Beyond* (2022), available at <https://scholarship.law.columbia.edu/books/96> (last visited on Nov. 8, 2025).

protection, and if so, who ought to be treated as the “author.”² Copyright regimes around the world are based on a notion of creativity that focuses on people. The conventional foundation of copyright asserts that creative expression arises from human knowledge, judgement, and individuality. The very concepts of originality, authorship, and creativity assume the presence of a living human creator who exercises choice, skill, and imagination. Unlike traditional tools such as cameras, editing software, or design tools AI systems can produce outputs with minimal or no human intervention. In several instances, the user’s role may be reduced to providing a short text prompt or selecting from multiple algorithmically produced variations. This raises profound questions about the extent of human contribution required for copyright protection and whether existing laws are capable of addressing such technologically mediated creativity.

Across jurisdictions, there is no uniformity in approach. Some countries adopt a strictly human authorship requirement, excluding any work lacking sufficient human creative control.³ Others recognize a functional or human contributor, such as the person who provides meaningful instructions or makes arrangements necessary for the creation of the work. A few jurisdictions take a more flexible, innovation-friendly approach, recognizing human, AI co-authorship or even extending derivative protection to AI-dominant works. This divergence results in substantial legal uncertainty for creators, industries, and policymakers, particularly because AI-generated works circulate globally across digital platforms. India finds itself in a transitional phase. The Copyright Act, 1957 continues to operate on the assumption that authorship is intrinsically human, and Indian courts have not yet confronted a fully autonomous AI creation case. The Parliamentary Standing Committee⁴ on Intellectual Property (2021) acknowledged the fact that AI should be used in such a way that maximum benefits are extracted from it but has refused to grant copyright protection to AI-generated works under the current Indian Copyright regime. As India is experiencing a lot of technological developments recently, lack of a dedicated AI-IPR framework will fail to incentivise the creators who are engaged in creating various arts/texts/sounds with the aid of AI.

² World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO), “Revised Issues Paper on Intellectual Property Policy and Artificial Intelligence” (2020), available at https://www.wipo.int/meetings/en/doc_details.jsp?doc_id=499504 (last visited Nov 10, 2025).

³ *ibid*

⁴ Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, *161st Parliamentary Standing Committee Report on Intellectual Property Rights* (2021).

In this paper, we will be study about the approaches followed by India and Canada in order to analyse the copyrightability of AI-generated works. The ultimate goal of this comparative study is to add to the ongoing conversation about AI and copyright by providing insights on how India may create a just and forward-looking copyright system. The analysis emphasises that the issue is no about whether AI should be incorporated into copyright law, but rather how and to what extent legal acknowledgement should be designed to boost innovation, safeguard creators, and uphold the integrity of copyright principles.

2. Brief History of Copyright

Generative Artificial Intelligence has prompted legal systems worldwide to reconsider fundamental principles of copyright law. Traditionally, copyright has been based on the idea that creativity is an exclusively human endeavour. It assumes that original works emerge from the author's intellect, judgment, personality, and individual choices.⁵ The rise of generative AI challenges this view by introducing technologies capable of producing text, images, music, and other forms of content independently or with limited human direction. Unlike earlier tools such as cameras or word processors, today's AI systems can not only assist creators but also generate seemingly original works on their own.

2.1 Creativity and Originality

This section analyses the rationale for safeguarding original works under copyright law, focussing on the definition and interpretation of originality across various jurisdictions. It is essential to elucidate that the term originality, in the context of copyright law, does not inherently correspond with the conventional interpretation of originality. Creative innovations represent merely a subset of artificial intelligence. Their contribution to society, however, is substantial, as they are capable of generating innovative ideas through software that resembles the structure of human neural networks. As computers become increasingly powerful and sophisticated, artificial intelligence systems and other forms of AI are likely to assume an integral part in the creative process, emerging as the main factors for creativity and innovation.⁶

⁵ Lionel Bently and Brad Sherman, *Intellectual Property Law* 104–106 (Oxford University Press, 2021).

⁶ Kalin Hristov, "Artificial Intelligence and the Copyright Dilemma" 57 *IDEA: The Journal of the Franklin Pierce Center for Intellectual Property* 431 (2017).

Another reason to provide copyright protection to original works can be found in Locke's Labour-desert theory, along with Hegel's personality theory.⁷ Locke explains how common goods can be transformed into private property. He argues that when individuals exert labour on common resources, they increase the value of these resources. The increase in value justifies allowing the individual who laboured, or who caused someone else to labour, to claim that resource as private property. While this theory is usually considered as the justification for having property rights, some argue that it more appropriately justifies intellectual property rights, including copyright. When authors draw on creative ideas or works that are in public domain to create a musical composition, a painting, or a book, they add value to the existing public goods and thus, deserve some form of reward.⁸ Opposed to this physical process, Hegel focuses more on the mental process behind creations. He argues that core of individuals existence is their will, and therefore, the creations of mind should be protected for individuals to achieve proper self-development. Again, this theory justifies having copyright laws because whenever author creates works, those works inherently reflect something from their personalities. By rewarding authors for original works (works that reflect personalities), copyright law acknowledges their efforts and fosters an environment where they can become the persons they wish to be.

The principal concern in this domain is the ambiguity surrounding the copyright protection of AI-generated works. These works are genuinely original, and had they been the product of physical labour, they would have received copyright protection. Then, why can AI-generated work not receive copyright protection, given that AI is the product of the efforts of multiple individuals as well? The undefined boundaries between human made and machine-generated expression challenges long-standing legal structures, particularly in the realm of copyright.⁹ At the far end of the spectrum, AI systems can generate complete works, such as paintings, poems, or musical compositions, with almost no human input beyond a short textual

⁷ John Locke, *Two Treatises of Government* (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1988), available at <https://www.yorku.ca/comminel/courses/3025pdf/Locke.pdf> (last visited Nov 10, 2025) G.W.F. Hegel, *Philosophy of Right* (T.M. Knox trans., Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1952), available at <https://www.marxists.org/reference/archive/hegel/works/pr/philosophy-of-right.pdf> (last visited Nov 11, 2025)

⁸ Sögüt Atilla, "A Comparative Study on the Originality of AI-Generated Artworks: What Can Copyright Laws Learn from Refik Anadol?" 36(1) *National Law School of India Review* (2025), available at <https://repository.nls.ac.in/nlsir/vol36/iss1/5/> (last visited Oct 30, 2025).

⁹ Harshal Chhabra and Kanishk Gaurav Pandey, "Balancing Indian Copyright Law with AI-Generated Content: The 'Significant Human Input' Approach" *IJLT Blog* (Feb. 26, 2024), available at: <https://forum.nls.ac.in/ijlt-blog-post/balancing-indian-copyright-law-with-ai-generated-content-the-significant-human-input-approach/> (last visited on Nov. 10, 2025).

instruction. These varying levels of involvement complicate legal analysis because copyright law has traditionally linked ownership to the presence of human intellectual labour.

The concept of authorship sits at the core of copyright law. Across jurisdictions, authorship presupposes the existence of a natural person whose intellectual effort produces the expressive form of the work.¹⁰ Authors are considered the source of creative choices, the bearers of moral rights, and the primary holders of economic rights.¹¹ Treating AI as an author is difficult because AI lacks legal personality and cannot bear legal duties, moral responsibility, or reputational interests. It cannot suffer harm to its integrity, claim attribution, or consent to licensing. These conceptual barriers explain why no major jurisdiction currently recognises AI as an independent author. Copyright systems are fundamentally built on the assumption that creativity originates from human intellect, and generative AI challenges this premise without fitting cleanly into existing categories.

Closely related is the concept of originality, which functions as the threshold for copyright protection.¹² Originality requirements differ across legal traditions, ranging from the “modicum of creativity” test in the United States and the creativity-plus-skill standard applied in India following *Eastern Book Company v. D.B. Modak*.¹³ Canada has assessed the term “originality”¹⁴, it was interpreted that the term originality holds that for works to be original, the creators must exercise their skill and judgement in the process of creation. Apart from fulfilling this criterion, the creations must also adhere to the following requirements:

1. The work must originate from the author, i.e., it must be independently created.
2. Skill must be exercised in contributing to the final expression of the work. The court has defined skill as the use of knowledge, developed attitude, and practised ability.
3. The works must involve judgment of the individual in the process of creation.

2.2 The Ownership and Liability Dilemma

These conceptual challenges within the Indian Copyright Regime give rise to several unsettled legal issues. One key issue relates to ownership: if AI cannot be considered an

¹⁰ Gautam Badlani, “Artificial Intelligence and the Need to Reform in Copyright Laws” 1(2) *Legal Spectrum Journal* 2 (2021).

¹¹ Supra note 10

¹² Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, 1869 UNTS 299 (1994), art. 27, available at https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/27-trips.pdf (last visited Nov 15, 2025).

¹³ *Eastern Book Company v. D.B. Modak*, (2008) 1 SCC 1.

¹⁴ *CCH Canadian Ltd. v. Law Society of Upper Canada*, (2004 SCC 13).

author, who should hold the rights to an AI-generated work, assuming such rights can exist? Possible claimants include the user who created the prompt, the developer who built the model, or the organisation that operates the platform. Each of these possibilities raises distinct theoretical and practical complications. Another major concern involves liability. When AI-generated content infringes existing copyright material, determining responsibility becomes complex. Should accountability rest with the developer who trained the model on copyrighted data, the user who generated the output, or the platform that enabled the process? So far, legal systems around the world have not reached consistent conclusions.¹⁵ India's position is particularly significant, as the country is rapidly advancing its technological sector while simultaneously reforming its intellectual property framework. In the absence of clear rules regarding AI-generated content, India faces inconsistencies, enforcement difficulties, and obstacles to innovation.¹⁶ A comparative study is therefore essential to guide potential legislative or judicial reforms. This chapter has laid the conceptual groundwork for such analysis by illustrating how AI-generated creativity redefines traditional notions of authorship, originality, and creativity.

3. Approaches for Granting Copyright Protection

3.1 Artificial Intelligence and the current Indian Copyright Office stance on works generated using Artificial Intelligence

India has not yet enacted explicit statutory provisions governing the copyrightability of AI-generated material, nor has the judiciary delivered authoritative rulings on the subject. A significant illustration of India's current uncertainty regarding the copyrightability of AI-generated works is found in the controversy surrounding the AI-assisted artwork *Suryast*, created by Ankit Saini, an IP lawyer and AI-artist.¹⁷ Saini used his proprietary AI model "Raghav" to generate the painting and filed a copyright application naming himself as the author while openly disclosing the use of AI as a creative tool. The Indian Copyright Office initially granted the registration, prompting public discussion that India had, for the first time, recognised an AI-generated artistic work. However, this initial decision was soon reversed.

¹⁵ Purvi Pokhariyal, Amit K. Kashyap, et al. (eds.), *Artificial Intelligence: Law and Policy Implications 2* (EBC Publishing, Lucknow, 2020).

¹⁶ Supra note 12

¹⁷ Joe Cahill, "From Original Photo to AI Art: SURYAST Lacks the Required Human Touch for Copyright Protection" *Our Take (Baker Botts LLC)* (Dec. 22, 2023), available at: <https://ourtake.bakerbotts.com/post/102ivxv/from-original-photo-to-ai-art-suryast-lacks-the-required-human-touch-for-copyrig> (last visited on Nov. 13, 2025).

The Office issued a withdrawal notice stating that the extent of human creativity had not been sufficiently demonstrated and that authorship under Section 2(d) of the Copyright Act, 1957 must be attributed only to a natural person. The Office further reasoned that although AI may be used as a tool, it cannot be recognised as an author or co-author, and mere prompting or curation does not satisfy the “skill and judgment” standard articulated by the Supreme Court in *Eastern Book Company v. D.B. Modak*.¹⁸ The *Suryast/Raghav* case therefore reveals the Copyright Office’s strict adherence to a human-authorship requirement and its reluctance to extend recognition to works where AI plays a substantial role in determining the final expression. Under Canadian copyright law, the concept of an “author” is fundamentally human-centred. The Canadian Copyright Act does not explicitly define the term “author,” but courts have consistently interpreted authorship as referring to a natural person, i.e., a human who uses his intellect and analytical skill in the creation of a work.¹⁹ The Canadian Copyright Laws²⁰ doesn’t grant protection to works generated by fully autonomous AI. However, AI-assisted works may be protected under Canadian law if the human contributor can demonstrate that they exercised meaningful skill and judgment in producing the final expression. Examples include selecting, arranging, modifying, or curating AI outputs in a way that reflects human creativity rather than mere mechanical application. In such cases, it is the human user, not the AI system, who is recognised as the author and therefore the owner of the copyright. This aligns with the CCH standard, which requires originality to flow from a human mind.²¹

3.2 Artificial Intelligence and the current Canadian Intellectual Property Office stance on works generated using Artificial Intelligence

As discussed earlier, Canada does not recognise AI as an author i.e., it does not grant copyright protection to AI-generated works. It only recognises the work that is made with significant human input, these works are granted copyright protection. Therefore, Canadian Copyright laws recognise AI-assisted works only when the human has used AI as a tool and utilised his own judgment and skill in the process. In its policy consultations on artificial intelligence and copyright, the Government of Canada clarified that works created using AI

¹⁸ Supra note 15.

¹⁹ *Gould Estate v. Stoddart Publishing Co. Ltd.*, 39 O.R. (3d) 555 (Ont. C.A. 1998), 1998 CanLII 5513.

²⁰ Copyright Act, R.S.C., 1985, c. C-42 (Canada), available at <https://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/acts/C-42/Index.html> (last visited on Nov. 17, 2025).

²¹ *Théberge v. Galerie d’Art du Petit Champlain inc.*, [2002] 2 S.C.R. 336, 2002 SCC 34, available at: <https://decisions.scc-csc.ca/scc-csc/scc-csc/en/item/1973/index.do> (last visited Nov. 17, 2025).

tools may qualify for protection only when a human author is responsible for the expressive elements of the work.²² Thus, if a user merely types prompts or relies on AI to autonomously determine artistic form, the resulting output is unlikely to meet Canada's originality threshold. Conversely, when a human meaningfully shapes the work by iterating prompts with intentional creative direction, editing AI outputs, or integrating them into a broader human-created composition the final work may be protected as an AI-assisted creation. In such cases, the human user is recognised as the author and first owner of the work, not the AI system that contributed to its creation.²³

Recent Canadian commentary further supports this approach. Legal analyses from Canadian practitioners emphasise that the originality requirement continues to be the primary gatekeeper for AI-assisted works, and authors must demonstrate identifiable human creativity in the production process. Government discussion papers also reiterate that AI lacks legal personality, cannot hold rights, and therefore cannot be considered the creator or owner of copyrighted material.²⁴ By acknowledging the copyrightability of AI-assisted works, Canada provides a balanced framework that supports technological innovation while preserving the doctrinal foundations of authorship.

4. Comparative Analysis

By comparing the two approaches, namely, India and Canada. It can be said India and Canada adopt human-centric copyright frameworks, yet their approaches to AI-assisted and AI-generated works diverge in nuance, administrative practice, and policy orientation. Both jurisdictions rely on originality standards that require human skill and judgment, but the way these standards are interpreted in the context of AI reflects different priorities and institutional attitudes.

²² Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada (ISED), *Consultation on a Modern Copyright Framework for Artificial Intelligence and the Internet of Things* (2021), available at: <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/strategic-policy-sector/en/marketplace-framework-policy/copyright-policy/consultation-modern-copyright-framework-artificial-intelligence-and-internet-things-0> (last visited Nov. 17, 2025).

²³ Norton Rose Fulbright, "Practical Commentary for Protecting Generative AI Art | Canada" (2024), available at: <https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en-ca/knowledge/publications/85e0e39d/practical-commentary-for-protecting-generative-ai-art> (last visited Nov. 17, 2025).

²⁴ Government of Canada, *Artificial Intelligence and Copyright — Discussion Papers* (2021–23), available at: <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/strategic-policy-sector/en/marketplace-framework-policy/copyright-policy> (last visited Nov. 18, 2025).

In India, the Copyright Act, 1957 recognises only a natural person as an author under Section 2(d).²⁵ Indian courts,²⁶ have held that originality requires a “flavour of creativity” combined with human skill and judgment. This judicial stance establishes a high threshold for AI-involved works. Administrative practice reinforces this human-centric interpretation: the AI-generated artwork *Suryast*, created by Ankit Saini using his model “Raghav,” was first granted and then revoked by the Indian Copyright Office because the human contribution was not shown to be sufficiently creative. India therefore, refuses copyright protection for purely AI-generated works and offers protection to AI-assisted works only where substantial human creativity is demonstrated. The Indian stance remains cautious, largely conservative, and doctrinally tied to traditional notions of authorship. However, the same painting “Suryast” was granted copyright protection by the Canadian Intellectual Property Office (CIPO). CIPO has recognised Artificial Intelligence as co-author of AI-Painting “Suryast”.

Canada’s legal structure is similar in foundation, but differs in emphasis and clarity. The Supreme Court of Canada²⁷ established the controlling originality test requiring “skill and judgment” from a human author. Canadian copyright law does not recognise AI as an author, and recent guidance from Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada (ISED) and the Canadian Intellectual Property Office (CIPO) confirms that fully autonomous AI outputs are not copyright-eligible because authorship must be human. However, Canada adopts a more explicit and policy-articulated approach than India: CIPO’s consultation papers state that AI-assisted works may be protected if the human exercises meaningful creative control such as modifying, selecting, arranging, or shaping the AI output. This positions Canada as more transparent and structured compared to India’s case-by-case administrative uncertainty.

5. Conclusion

Given the remarkable capabilities of generative AI technology, the growing number of artworks produced using AI tools is unsurprising. However, since these works are not created through conventional artistic processes, they raise important questions about their eligibility for copyright protection. The analysis comparing India and Canada shows that AI-generated creativity has put copyright law at a key turning point. Earlier chapters pointed out this

²⁵ The Copyright Act (Act 14 of 1957), s. 2(d).

²⁶ Supra note 15

²⁷ Supra note 16

tension between the originality criteria and AI-generated works. In this paper, two different approaches have been discussed. India and Canada does stick to a traditional human-centric approach for granting copyright protections. But Canada uses a practical law-based model. It gives authorship in the cases of AI-assisted works, especially when AI has been used as a tool by a human. It can be concluded that if, when interpreting and applying copyright requirements to AI-generated artworks in accordance with established case law, originality can be identified, then the uncertainty of artists or lawyers to draft new methodologies for creating or managing artistic works should not hinder the copyright protection of AI-generated artworks. It is suggested that India should establish a dedicated framework to address cases involving AI and IPR. AI can also be used by various creators to monitor any instances of copyright infringement of any digital creation.